

Microbial Landscape of Acute and Chronic Osteomyelitis in Pediatric Patients

Ergashev V. A.

Technical College of Public Health named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Uzbekistan, Navoi city, S. Ayni street

Article information:

Manuscript received: 19 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 20 Sep 2024; **Published:** 21 Oct 2024

Abstract: In this article, based on the results of microbiological studies in 68 pediatric patients with acute and chronic osteomyelitis, infectious pathogens collected in a bacteriological laboratory from biological material (blood and pus) obtained from pediatric patients were studied, which may have various aspects, features and differences, associated with a form of osteomyelitis. Based on the research results, the specificity and differences of the etiological agents that provoke osteomyelitis in children were identified.

Material and methods Biological material (blood and pus) obtained from 68 children treated with acute and chronic osteomyelitis, as well as evidence-based medical principles and statistical methods were used in the organization and conduct of research.

Conclusions:

- In accordance with the age of the sick children, the composition of etiological agents, the degree of occurrence of microbial landscape, differences in the indicators of the percentage of the multiplication of triggers with each other were found.
- When the incidence rate of osteomyelitis compared to the age of children was estimated, it was noted that acute osteomyelitis was more common compared to chronic manifestations.
- In acute osteomyelitis, gram-positive cocci were found to be important, while in chronic form, gram-negative bacteria, microscopic fungi, and anaerobes were found to be important.

Keywords: osteomyelitis, strain, monoculture, assumption of microorganisms, biological material, etiological agent.

The urgency of the problem

Today, the incidence of acute and chronic forms of osteomyelitis among children is one of the urgent problems that need to be solved in the medical field due to the high rate of complications, disability indicators and economic damage [1, 2, 4, 5].

When children's body is affected by external negative influences, the body's immune system and protective factors decrease, resulting in the development of acute and chronic osteomyelitis caused by disease-causing microorganisms.

Along with gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria, various microscopic fungi and anaerobic bacteria are important in the formation of acute and chronic osteomyelitis [3, 4, 6, 7].

In acute and chronic osteomyelitis in children, early bacteriological diagnosis through comparative study

and analysis of the characteristics of etiological agents, microbial landscape, pathogenic mechanism, rational antibiotic therapy based on the characteristics of etiological agents, is one of the current medical problems.

Research results and discussion

In this study, a total of 68 children with acute (n=45) and chronic (n=23) manifestations of osteomyelitis were studied.

Distribution shares of children with acute and chronic osteomyelitis according to disease manifestations are presented in Figure 1.

The tendency to meet acute and chronic osteomyelitis - $66.2 \pm 5.7\%$ (n=45) versus $33.8 \pm 5.7\%$ (n=23), respectively - $R < 0.001$. In acute and chronic osteomyelitis, a large difference in the intensity of differences was observed, this parameter reached 2.0 times.

[3, 7].

The identified causes of diagnosed osteomyelitis were as follows (Fig. 2): post-traumatic osteomyelitis was $41.2 \pm 6.0\%$ (n=28).

When comparing the incidence rate of the manifestations of the disease in relation to the age of the patient, acute osteomyelitis was more frequent than the chronic form ($R < 0.001$) - 17.0 times in 0-6 year olds, 2.5 times in 7-14 year olds, 1.5 times in 15-18 year olds, respectively. We watched for a while.

In accordance with the age of the patients, it was found that there were differences in the composition of etiological agents, the level of encounter, the microbial landscape, and the indicators of the percentage of pathogens (Table 1).

Table 1 Indicators of microbial landscape of etiologic agents from children with osteomyelitis, n=68

Trigger	Monoculture		A/M		Total	
	AN	%	AN	%	AN	%
S.aureus	15	19,2±4,5	10	12,8±3,8	25	32,0±5,3
S.epidermidis	5	6,4±2,8	7	9,0±3,2	12	15,4±4,1
Enterococcus spp	2	2,6±1,8	0	0	2	2,6±1,8
S.saprophyticus	1	1,3±1,2	1	1,3±1,2	2	2,6±1,8
Gram positive cocci total	23	29,5±5,2	18	23,1±4,8	41	52,6±5,7
P.aeruginosa	9	11,5±3,6	2	2,6±1,8	11	14,1±3,5
E.coli	6	7,7±3,0	5	6,4±2,8	11	14,1±3,5
Klebsiella spp	3	3,8±4,7	2	2,6±1,8	5	6,4±2,8
Proteus spp	2	2,6±1,8	4	5,1±2,5	6	7,7±3,0
Enterobacter spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
Gram negative bacteria total	20	25,6±4,9	15	19,3±4,5	35	44,9±5,6
Candida spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
Total strains	43	55,1±5,6	35	44,9±5,6	78	100,0

Note: A/M - association of microorganisms; AN - in absolute numbers.

S.aureus and P.aeruginosa were found to be dominant in monoculture in children with osteomyelitis. Association of microorganisms: in 18 cases - 36 strains were recovered. In the form of the association of microorganisms, leadership was observed in S.aureus + E.coli association, followed by S.aureus + S.epidermidis, S.aureus + Candida spp, S.epidermidis + Proteus spp, S.epidermidis + Enterobacter spp. [4].

The results of the distribution of etiological agents from children with osteomyelitis according to the form of the disease (Table 2) are presented.

Table 2 Distribution of etiological agents from children with osteomyelitis according to disease manifestations

Triggers	Acute, n=23		Chronic, n=45		Total, n=68	
	AN	%	AN	%	AN	%
E.coli	3	3,8±4,7	8	10,3±3,4	11	14,1±3,5
Proteus spp	2	2,6±1,8	4	5,1±2,5	6	7,7±3,0
Klebsiella spp	0	0	5	6,4±2,8	5	6,4±2,8
Enterobacter spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
P.aeruginosa	0	0	11	14,1±3,5	11	14,1±3,5
Gram negative bacteria total	5	6,4±2,8	30	38,5±5,5	35	44,9±5,6
S.aureus	14	18,0±4,4	11	14,0±3,5	25	32,0±5,3
S.epidermidis	3	3,8±4,7	9	11,6±3,6	12	15,4±4,1
S.saprophyticus	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
Enterococcus spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
Gram negative bacteria total	17	21,8±4,7	24	30,8±5,2	41	52,6±5,7
Candida spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	2	2,6±1,8
Total strains	22	28,2±5,1	56	71,8±5,1	78	100,0
Ungrown	1		3		4	

Note: AN- is in absolute numbers.

When biological samples from children with acute and chronic osteomyelitis are collected in a microbiological laboratory:

- in acute forms of osteomyelitis in sick children, etiological agents belonging to 4 genera and species were isolated, and in chronic osteomyelitis, etiological agents of 10 genera and species were isolated (2.25 times more);
- *Klebsiella* spp, *P.aeruginosa* and *Candida* spp did not germinate in acute osteomyelitis, they were identified as etiological agents in chronic osteomyelitis;
- Among the causative agents, gram-positive cocci were significantly more common than gram-negative bacteria, anaerobes and *Candida* spp. *S.aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *E.coli*, *P. aeruginosa* are the leading microorganisms that cause osteomyelitis. It was found that there were convincing differences between gram-positive cocci and gram-negative bacteria in the monoculture condition;
- recognized as the most common etiological agent in acute osteomyelitis, while leadership in chronic osteomyelitis was observed in *P.aeruginosa*.
- Therefore, the role of *S. aureus* in the acute course of the disease, and the role of *P. aeruginosa* in chronic osteomyelitis;
- it should be noted that *Klebsiella* spp, *P.aeruginosa*, *Bacteroides* spp, *Candida* spp, which do not germinate as an etiological agent in the acute form of osteomyelitis, germinate in large quantities in the chronic form of the disease;
- in the acute form of the disease compared to the chronic form, gram-positive cocci were reliably detected, while the opposite was observed for gram-negative bacteria, microscopic fungi and anaerobes. Therefore, it was found that gram-positive cocci are more important in the acute form, while gram-negative bacteria, microscopic fungi and anaerobes are more important in the chronic form.

We have provided information on the compatibility of etiological agents grown from children with osteomyelitis to disease-causing factors, and data on etiological agents grown in the bacteriological laboratory from examined biological materials (table 3).

3 – Table Aspects of etiological agents corresponding to disease-causing factors

Trigger	post-traumatic, n=28		Hematogenous, n=29		No reason, n=11	
	MyT	%	MyT	%	MyT	%
<i>S.aureus</i>	24	30,8±5,2	1	1,3±1,2	0	0
<i>S.epidermidis</i>	9	11,5±3,6	2	2,6±1,8	1	1,3±1,2
<i>S.saprophyticus</i>	2	2,6±1,8	0	0	0	0
<i>Enterococcus</i> spp	1	1,3±1,2	1	1,3±1,2	0	0
Gram positive cocci total	36	46,2±5,6	4	5,2±2,5	1	1,3±1,2
<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	8	10,3±3,4	0	0	3	3,8±4,7
<i>E.coli</i>	6	7,7±3,0	3	3,8±4,7	2	2,6±1,8
<i>Proteus</i> spp	4	5,1±2,5	1	1,3±1,2	1	1,3±1,2
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp	1	1,3±1,2	4	5,1±2,5	0	0
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp	0	0	2	2,6±1,8	0	0
Gram negative bacteria total	19	24,4±4,9	10	12,8±3,8	6	7,7±3,0
<i>Candida</i> spp	2	2,6±1,8	0	0	0	0
Total strains	57	73,2±5,0	14	18,0±4,4	7	9,0±3,2
Ungrown	1		3		0	

Note: Mut is in absolute numbers.

Gram-positive cocci, *S.aureus*, Gram-negative bacteria, *P.aeruginosa* and *Candida* spp. In the development of hematogenous osteomyelitis, the microbial landscape has changed as etiological agents, i.e. gram-positive cocci, *S.epidermidis*, gram-negative bacteria, *Klebsiella* spp and *E.coli*, the cause of which has not been determined, in osteomyelitis, gram-negative bacteria *P.aeruginosa* took the lead as etiological agents. *Candida* spp, which grew in posttraumatic osteomyelitis, did not grow in hematogenous and unexplained osteomyelitis.

List of references

1. Inamdjanova I.U., Khamraeva Sh.E., Khasanov A.I. Sovershenstvovanie medikamentoznoy terapii ostrogo odontogennogo osteomyelita nijney chelyusti u detey // Uzbekiston medical journal. - Tashkent, 2016. - #5. - S.102-105.
2. Skvortsov A.P., Gilmutdinov M.R., Akhtyamov I.F. Prophylaktika ortopedicheskikh posledstviy v oblasti tazobedrennogo sustava u detey s epimetafizarnym osteomyelitom // Vestnik travmatologii i ortopedii im. N.N. Priorova. - 2011. - #3. - S. 44-47.
3. V.A.Ergashev. Kharakteristika mikrobnogo landscape patogenov pri osteomyelitax u detey // Central Asian Journal of Medical and natural Science 2 (3), 25-30, 2021.
4. Ergashev V.A. Description of the Microbial Landscape of Causative Agents of Acute Osteomyelitis Observed in Children // European multidisciplinary journal of modern science. Volume: 16 | Mar-2023. P. 74-78.
5. Langlois DK, Sutton DA, Swenson CL, Bailey CJ, Wiederhold NP, Nelson NC. Clinical, morphological and molecular characterization of *Penicillium canis* sp. nov., isolated from a dog with osteomyelitis // J Clin Microbiol. - 2014. - Vol 52(7). - P.2447-2453.
6. Krajewski J., Bode-Böger S.M., Tröger U., Martens-Lobenhoffer J., Mulrooney T. Successful treatment of extensively drug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* osteomyelitis using a colistin- and tobramycin-impregnated PMMA spacer // Int J Antimicrob Agents . - 2014. - Vol 44(4). - P.363-366.
7. Seng P., Bayle S., Vernier M., Romain F., Allier A., Magalon G., Casanova D., Stein A. Rib osteomyelitis: an uncommon complication of breast implant infection // J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg . - 2015. - Vol 68(3). - P.431-432.